

**STREET HAWKING AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GIRL
CHILD IN CALABAR MUNICIPAL LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA,
CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The study looked into the connection between street hawking and girl child's academic performance in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study primarily investigated the association between street hawking and a girl child academic performance through her school attendance issue and the association between street hawking and her academic performance as a result of her lateness to school. Cognitive child development theory served as the theoretical underpinning for the investigation. 200 respondents were chosen using a simple random sampling technique via the balloting process. A 20-item survey titled "street hawking and academic performance of girl child (SHAPOGC)" was used to gather data. For statistical analysis, the chi-square was employed, with a degree of freedom of 1. According to the study's findings, street hawking has a detrimental impact on girls' academic performance. And a significance level of 0.05 were applied to the testing of two hypotheses. The findings demonstrated a substantial correlation between street hawking and a girl child's

academic performance as measured by her attendance at school, as well as a significant association between street hawking and a girl child's academic performance as a result of arriving late to school. Based on the findings, it was suggested that the government enact and enforce laws prohibiting child hawking during school hours, that religious and traditional leaders, non-governmental organizations, and educators educate and raise awareness among parents about the risks of enlisting their children in child labor through street hawking, and that the government work with school principals to address the issues of late arrivals, poor academic performance, and non-attendance among girls in order to improve their academic performance.

Keywords: Street hawking, Academic performance, Girl child, School attendance problem, lateness to school

INTRODUCTION

The issue of girls not attending school and hawking on the streets to make a living or for other reasons is a worldwide one. Globally, the problem's severity varies (Adeyemi, 2012; Alaye, 2021). The problem is becoming worse and is now a troubling social issue on a global scale. Approximately 60% of African youth aged 15 and older are disadvantaged members of society who work, live, and survive on the streets in the name of street hawking, and one-fifth of African children aged 6 to 11 do not attend school (UNESCO, 2020). This is particularly true in developing nations where the demands for children to be enrolled in school are not met. Girl children's social isolation from street selling has been a global problem for many years and continues to this day. UNESCO (2020) estimates that 100 million children of both sexes are growing up selling on the streets worldwide. As a result, their incapacity to attend school significantly restricts their socioeconomic advancement and social infrastructure (Hassen & Maus, 2018). From Kenya to Senegal and Togo to Nigeria, street hawking is a viable way for the girl child to get money. In Nigeria, girls are left to fend for themselves or their families by chasing cars to sell on the streets, which has an adverse effect on their academic performance and academics.

The knowledge and abilities that students have mastered in a subject or course are referred to as academic performance. In essence, it is a gauge of how well pupils have done on the several test questions that have been assigned to them in accordance with certain learning standards that have been established by qualified teachers. In addition to ranking students according to the educational standards they have attained pass, credit, distinction, high distinction, and so forth, academic performance is determined by how well students perform on assessment items like essays, tests, and exams. This is primarily the case when street hawking is not a factor (Uyang, Abanbeshie, Uyang & Aniah, 2023; Uyang, Abanbeshie, Basse & Omono, 2023; Uyang, Eba, Abanbeshie, Omono & Oben, 2024). Uyang, Abanbeshie, Ikpi and Edem (2024) argued that academic performance is a crucial indicator of academic success because it opens opportunities to further education and well-paying employment, demonstrating the value of educating children over exploiting them for short-term financial gain. Additionally, they emphasized that in order for women to have the same opportunities as men in the educational and employment sectors, they must be equally prepared academically and refrain from engaging in street hawking during class hours. This is because hawking is a factor that

has a negative impact on school attendance, excellent performance, class participation, and early class attendance.

The academic performance of girls has been negatively impacted by the high prevalence and incidence of street hawking during school hours in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, specifically in Ikot Ishie, Marian, Watt, and Etta Agbor, to name a few locations. Some girls' academic development is hampered by hawking because they are unable to attend school or because of poor grades, test non-participation, absenteeism, and lateness, among other reasons (Maybin & Woodhead, 2003; Uyang, Ejeje & Aniah, 2016). Exposure to hawking causes the girl child to consistently arrive late, lose focus in class, and receive poor grades, all of which have an impact on their general performance and education. In Nigeria, especially in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area and Cross River State, street hawking by female children have detrimental effect on their academic performance. In light of this, the purpose of this study is to investigate the association between street hawking and the academic performance of girls in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Numerous attempts to prevent, lessen, and manage the prevalence of Child Street hawking in Nigeria, Cross River State, and Calabar Municipal Local Government Area have been unsuccessful, despite the efforts of both government agencies and non-governmental organizations such as the Ministry of Women Affairs, UNICEF, USAID, etc. Since many girls are found hawking on the streets of Calabar Municipal Local Government Area during school hours, which jeopardizes their schooling and academic performance, which determines their educational development, the National Assembly's proactive child rights acts, which were created over the years to protect girls from being exploited for financial gain in violation of their fundamental right to an education, have proven to be a mirage and forecast how they will contribute to the nation's development. Since a person's educational background has a significant impact on their success in the workplace, education is crucial for all aspects of human development, especially the development of girls. Many organizations, including UNICEF, USAID, and the 2030 Sustainable Millennium Goals, are interested in the issue of girl children being subjected to hawking in relation to their academic performance and studies.

Like the majority of Nigerian metropolitan areas, Calabar Municipality is teeming with the girl child engaging in various forms of "trading" on the streets during school hours. This has led to the occurrence of lateness, absenteeism, exam malpractice, poor performance, and non-participation in tests, which in turn causes poor academic performance or, alternatively, permanent school dropout, which is detrimental to the socioeconomic development of the nation and the health of the girl child (Uyang, Ejeje & Aniah, 2016; Uyang, Abanbeshie, Ikpi & Edem, 2024). The involvement of girls in street hawking is the cause of the issues of failure, lateness, absenteeism, and lack of participation in tests. The street hawking phenomena in Calabar Municipal is concerning, and several educators and school principals have called for steps to assist stop it before it has a deeper impact on Nigerian society.

Due to their participation in street selling, girls have performed poorly academically, which necessitates a remedy. Numerous research have looked into the association between a girl child's academic performance and street hawking. These studies, however, did not particularly

examine the association between street hawking and girls' academic performance in a comprehensive manner. Thus, the goal of this study was to bridge this gap. The study's goal is to find out how street hawking affects girls' academic performance in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria, by looking into lateness to school and school attendance issues.

Objectives of the study

The study's goal is to find out how street hawking and girls' academic performance relate to one another in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. In particular, the study aims to:

Statement of Hypotheses

1. In the Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria, there is no significant association between street hawking and the academic performance of girls as measured by their school attendance issues.

2. In the Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria, there is no significant association between street hawking and the academic performance of girls who arrive late to school.

Literature review

Street Hawking and School Attendance Problem

Academic performance and performance deficits have been connected to issues with school attendance, particularly absenteeism from classes (Burton, Marshal & Chisolm, 2014; Uyang, Abanbeshie & Eyang, 2018; Attwood & Croll, 2015). An increased risk of future financial, marital, and mental health issues are among the long-term consequences of a school attendance issue that results in dropout (Rocque, Jennings, Pquero, Ozkan & Farrington, 2017). Researchers have found that a number of factors, including peer pressure, family troubles, parental carelessness, and child hawking, contribute to girls' difficulties attending school (Maxwell, 2016; McKee & Caldarella, 2016). One risk factor that has a direct impact on secondary school students' academic performance and attendance at school is street hawking (Epstein & Sheldon, 2002). In a South African study, Chaiké and Olusegun (2019) discovered that the girl child who is forced to work as street hawker for any reason seldom have enough time to study because they struggle to balance their schedules. They claim that they are constantly spotted wandering the streets during school hours, primarily in the morning when classes are in session and crucial topics or subjects are being taught. They also claim that they may not be able to make up missed classes since they are preoccupied with selling the items they currently possess. This behavior discourages students from going to school, which has an impact on their academic performance. Since they are constantly spotted on the street by their classmates or friends, girls who hawk have a harder time attending and adjusting to school than their peers who do not engage in the activity. This is because they may be experiencing low self-esteem and sadness.

Children who hawk during school hours may experience adverse effects on their academic performance, including absenteeism, low academic performance, and eventual dropout due to poor academic performance (Chaiké & Olusegun, 2019). Another study by Azubuike (2015) in

Nigeria discovered that, for whatever reason, girl child hawking typically impacts school time, attention, and non-participation in tests or assignments. As a result, less attention is paid to their academic work, which irritates their capacity for seriousness and leads to absenteeism and failure. According to Azubuike's (2015) research, teachers typically characterize the majority of adolescents who engage in street hawking as being more aggressive, nervous, and distracting than those from non-involved households. Seeing their friends go to school while hawking goods in the morning all day makes them vulnerable against their right, wish, and desire for education. This has a significant impact on their academic performance, and they may drop out to face their lifelong hawking (Uyang, Abanbeshie, Ikpi & Edem, 2024). Girl children who are found to be affected by the incidence of street hawking sometimes accept the situation as normal because they are powerless to stop it.

Street Hawking and Lateness to School

One of the issues that school administrators deal with is street hawking and lateness to school (Ojigbo & Obeta, 2013). Students' behavior is shaped by the way the school environment is set up. Students that arrive late violate the timeliness principle, and their academic performance may suffer if it is not addressed early on and becomes a habit (Breezes, Markey & Woll, 2010). When someone arrives to a location after the designated time, it is often referred to as being late. It is the incapacity of a person to arrive at a location at the scheduled time. People that arrive late are referred to as late (Lauby, 2019). According to Ojigbo and Obeta (2013), lateness to school is defined as failing to arrive to school events on time, which may result in students' academic performance and the failure to meet school goals and objectives. One of the most prevalent maladaptive behaviors among secondary school girls, particularly those whose children are exposed to street hawking, have been found to be lateness to school (Ohigbo & Obeta, 2013).

According to Ofoegbu and Igbokwe (2021), a lot of secondary school pupils are not time-conscious, which leads to their lateness to class. Several studies have shown that this is because girls are involved in street hawking. The current school curriculum provides continuity and advancement in people's learning, and any absences will negatively impact a student's capacity to engage with and gain from the curriculum. Overall, frequent lateness to class could be one of the causes of Nigerian students' declining academic performance standards (Ofoegbu & Ogbokwe, 2021). According to Ochujor (2014), numerous measures have been implemented to reduce the incidence of lateness, such as flogging and sanctions, but this has not resolved the problem because street hawking has not been able to be stopped as a predictor of student lateness. Ochujor (2014) emphasized that parents, teachers, school administrators, and others have expressed genuine worry about it. Being late to school can have a negative impact on students' academic performance and likelihood of dropping out, as well as cause them to struggle to maintain accurate records, meet instructional targets, and harm the school's reputation. Ofoegbu and Igbokwe (2021) listed the reasons why students arrive late to school, including transportation issues, household chores, and student indolence brought on by a high level of street hawking. Students lose valuable time when they are missing or arrive late, and they might not know how to approach their academics. Students should therefore arrive for class promptly. Students that arrive late to class cause disruptions and are unfair to other

students (Abubakare, Bashir & Vera, 2015). Being late to class is a problem that has an adverse effect on students' academic performance.

Theoretical Framework

Cognitive Child Development Theory

Alfred Adler and Jean Piaget propounded the cognitive theory of child development in 1980. According to this view, a child exposed to street hawking is likely to exhibit the following characteristics as a result of the negative effects associated with child maltreatment. Irrational thinking, beliefs, and unconscious cognitive schemes are examples of thinking errors that impact a child's worldview, academic pursuits, and attitudes toward objects. The idea makes the assumption that children think through situations in accordance with developmental stages. Generally speaking, when a child experiences detachment due to a high level of street hawking engagement, their thinking differs from that of other children who have peaceful family relationships. The idea clarifies the reasoning behind anything that motivates behavior. A child's emotional and psychological well-being is greatly impacted when they are constantly hawking on the streets while other girl children are seen attending school. This has a significant impact on the child's personality and alters their feelings and behavior, particularly when they start to feel deprived, which leads to negative thinking and cognitive limitations. Children cognitive development and abilities are impacted when they are mistreated, abused, assaulted, or injured because they are unable to make successful sales. This leads to mistakes in thinking and affects how the children approaches their academics.

Children think differently than adults, according to Adler and Piaget. They also presented a stage theory of cognitive development, which states that children actively participate in learning about the world and are viewed as tiny "scientists" who actively create their knowledge and comprehension of their immediate surroundings. However, if children are consumed by their own overall development, it can skew their learning habits in all directions. According to Adler and Piaget, socialization enhances learning and that a child learns from peers, family, school, and the church. However, when children are forced to work as street vendor, they may not have the time to learn from these socialization agents, which can have a significant impact on the children because learning occurs through socialization, which creates a calm environment for the development of positive learning habits that can support exceptional academic performance.

Material and Method

The questionnaire was the primary tool used to gather data for this cross-sectional survey. Both open-ended and closed-ended questions were included in the questionnaire's framework. The purpose of the closed-ended questions was to extract information that would make data collection and hypothesis testing simple. The purpose of the few open-ended questions was to provide respondents the freedom to freely discuss street hawking and girls' academic performance. The study was carried out at Cross River State's Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. The study's sample size consisted of 200 respondents, both male and female, and the sample was chosen using simple random selection. Randomization was ensured by using the balloting procedure. Marian Market, State Housing Estate, Federal Housing Estate, Akim, and Edim Otop were the five locations that were chosen. A total of 200 respondents took

part in the survey, which was divided into these groupings. From each cluster, forty (40) responders were chosen. Two hundred (200) respondents in all were chosen for the research. Both primary and secondary sources of data were used in the investigation. The primary source of data was structured surveys; secondary sources included information from journals, textbooks, the internet, and other sources. At the 0.05 level of significance, the data gathered via the questionnaire was analyzed using the chi-square statistical technique. The appropriate statistical methods were used to edit, code, and analyze the data.

Discussion of Results

Date Presentation

Table 1: Distribution of respondents' socio-demographic data

Variables	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	80	40
Female	120	60
Total	200	100
Age		
Under 15 years	15	7.5
15-25	90	45
26-35	60	30
36-45	15	7.5
46 above	20	10
Total	200	100
Marital Status		
Single	95	47.5
Single	60	30
Married	25	12.5
Divorced	12	6

Widow	8	4
Total	200	100
Occupation		
Self employed	84	42
Civil servants	45	22.5
Unemployed	44	27.5
Others	16	8
Total	200	100
Educational level		
FSLC	40	20
SSCE/NECO	65	32.5
OND/NCE	46	24
B.Sc/BA	32	16
M.Sc and others	15	7.5
Total	200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

The respondents' socio-demographic information is displayed in Table 1. Sex-wise, 60% (N=120) were female and 40% (N=80) were male. This indicates that women made up the majority of the respondents. This may be explained by the fact that women are more impacted by the issue being studied. 7.5% of respondents were under 15 years old (N=15), 45% were 15–25 years old (N=90), 30% were 26–35 years old (N=60), 7.5% were 36–45 years old (N=15), and 10% were 46 years old and older (N=20). This suggests that the largest percentage of research participants were between the ages of 15 and 25. In terms of marital status, 12.5% (N=25) were separated, 6% (N=12) were divorced, 4% (N=8) were widowed, 47.5% (N=95) were single, and 30% (N=60) were married. This indicates that the majority of those surveyed were unmarried. 42% (N=84) of the population in the occupation were self-employed, 22.5% (N=45) were civil servants, 27.5% (N=55) were jobless, and 8% (N=16) fell into another group. This indicates that the vast majority of those surveyed work for themselves. 20% (N=50) had FSLC, 32.5% (N=65) had SSCE/NECO Certificate, 24% (N=48) had OND/NCE, 16% (N=32) had B.Sc. or BA, and 7.5% (N=15) had M.Sc. and other credentials. This suggests that

SSCE/NECO respondents made up the majority of the sample and were easily accessible to complete the survey.

Hypothesis one

In the Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, there is no significant association between street hawking and the academic performance of girls as measured by their attendance at school.

Table 2: Chi-square (X²) statistical analysis of the association between street hawking and school attendance problem

Variables	Responses		Total	X ² -value
	Yes	No		
Street hawking	125 (114.75)	10 (20.50)	135	4.6
School attendance problem	45 (55.25)	20 (9.75)	65	
Total	170	30	200	

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

*figures in bracket represent the expected values.

Significance at 0.05 level

X² = 3.84

Df=1

$$X^2 = \left(\frac{(O-E)^2}{E} \right)$$

Result:

Level of significance = 0.05

Degree of freedom = 1

Critical value = 3.84

Calculated value = 4.60

According to respondents' answers in Table 2, there is significant association between street hawking and academic performance of girl child as measured by their attendance at school. With a level of significance of 0.05 and a degree of freedom of 1, the calculated value of x² of 4.60 in Table 2 was determined to be statistically higher than the critical value of 3.84. In light of this, we support the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis, which holds that there is a meaningful connection between street hawking and girls' academic performance in Calabar Municipal LGA as measured by their school attendance

Hypothesis two:

In the Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, there is no significant association between street hawking and the academic performance of girls who arrive late to school.

Table 3: Chi-square (χ^2) statistical analysis of the association between street hawking and lateness to school

Variables	Responses		Total	X2-value
	Yes	No		
Street hawking	30 (48.10)	100 (81.90)	130	17.26
Lateness to school	44 (25.90)	26 (44.10)	70	
Total	74	126	200	

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

*figures in bracket represent the expected values.

Significance at 0.05 level

$\chi^2 = 3.84$

Df=1

$\chi^2 = \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$

Result:

Level of significance = 0.05

Degree of freedom = 1

Critical value = 3.84

Calculated value = 17.26

Since the computed χ^2 value of 17.26 from table 3 was found to be statistically greater than the critical value with a degree of freedom of 1 and a level of significance of 0.05, we accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant association between street hawking and the academic performance of girls in the Calabar Municipal Local Government Area who arrive late to school.

Discussion of Finding

Street hawking and academic performance of girl child through school attendance problem

The results of the study, which are shown in table 2, show a strong association between street hawking and girls' academic performance as measured by their attendance issues at school. This perspective was reinforced by Maxwell (2016), and McKee and Caldarella (2016), who argued that a number of variables, including peer pressure, family problems, parental carelessness, and child hawking, among others, contribute to girls' difficulties attending school. These results are consistent with a South African study by Chauke and Olusegun (2019). They discovered that children who are forced to work as street vendors for any reason don't always have enough time for their education since they struggle to make time. They claim that they are constantly spotted wandering the streets during school hours, primarily in the morning when crucial lessons or subjects are being taught. They also claim that they may not be able to make up missed classes because they are worried about selling the things they currently own, which prevents them from going to school and lowers their academic performance.

Street hawking and academic performance of girl child as a result of lateness to school

The findings in Table 3 demonstrate a substantial association between street hawking and a girl child's academic performance as a result of arriving late to school. The findings are in line with those of Ofoegbu and Igbokwe (2021), who noted that a large number of secondary school pupils lack time awareness, which contributes to their lateness to class. Numerous studies have indicated that this is because of the involvement of girls in street hawking. The results support the claims made by Abubakare, Bashir and Vera (2015) that students who are absent or late to school lose valuable time and may become disoriented when it comes to their education. They went on to say that students who arrive late to class are disruptive and unfair to their peers.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The life of a girl child is negatively impacted by street hawking in numerous ways. Children's physical and psychological development, as well as their general well-being and academic performance, are all impacted by street hawking. The study consequently recommended that:

1. Government should develop and implement regulations banning child hawking during school hours.
2. Teachers, NGOs, religious leaders, and traditional authorities should inform and raise awareness among parents about the risks of enlisting their girl children in street hawking as child labor. Parents and guardians should be made aware that letting their girl child work for the family during school hours exposes them to moral and physical harm that could ruin their future by causing lateness, poor performance, and absenteeism.
3. In order to improve girls' academic performance, the government should collaborate with school principals to address the issues of lateness, poor performance, and absence from school.

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